

DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF β -RESORCYLIC ACID.

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The dissociation constant K_1^a of β -resorcylic acid has been determined by the measurement of the E. M. F. of the cell without any liquid junction

The corrected value of K_1^a in pure water is found to be 6.05×10^{-4} at 30° .

In the course of a systematic research on the dissociation constants of hydroxybenzoic acids (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1938, **21A**, 417) we have shown that the order of the first dissociation constants (K_1^a) is *ortho* > *meta* > *H* > *para*, while that of the second dissociation constants (K_2^a), for which there are no previous values in literature, is the reverse. The first dissociation constant of the gallic acid is appreciably less than that of benzoic acid, which is surprising in view of the fact that the OH groups, due to the electron attracting di-pole, should increase the strength of the acid. It was, therefore, interesting to study the first dissociation constants of α -, β - and γ -resorcylic acids. The previous results of the dissociation constants for the resorcylic acids were determined by the conductivity method (*cf.* Ostwald, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1889, **3**, 249; Süss, *Monatsh*, 1905, **26**, 1331) and were not corrected for the effect of interionic attraction. In the present paper we have presented the results obtained for the dissociation constants of β -resorcylic acid by measuring the E.M.F. of the cells

The value of K_1^a is 6.05×10^{-4} as compared with K_1^c 5.16×10^{-4} and 4.96×10^{-4} of Ostwald and Süss respectively.

In the previous paper we had determined the dissociation constants by the method of potentiometric titrations after measuring the p_H at various stages of the titration. The p_H at any point was computed from the E.M.F. of the cell

The junction potential between the solution X and saturated calomel was assumed to be small and neglected which really is not the case (*J. Bureau Standards*, 1936, **16**, 575). It was, therefore, necessary to use a method in which there will be no uncertainty regarding the junction potential.

The use of silver—silver chloride electrode for the determination of dissociation constants of weak acids has been described by Harned and co-workers (*J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 5079; 1932, **54**, 1350). The method consists of measuring the electromotive force of the cells of the type

The dissociation constant K is calculated according to the equation

$$E - E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{m_{\text{HAN}} m_{\text{Cl}}}{m_{\text{AN}}} = - \frac{RT}{F} \ln K'$$

$$= - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{HAN}} \gamma_{\text{Cl}}}{\gamma_{\text{AN}}} - \frac{RT}{F} \ln K_1^c$$

where E is the electromotive force of the cell of the above type and the terms represented by m represent the ionic concentrations of the salts in solution. E_o was determined by measuring the E.M.F. of the cell

containing hydrochloric acid of various concentrations. Its value was found to be 0.21920 at 30° in agreement with that reported by

Harned (*loc. cit.*). At zero ionic concentration the term $\ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{HAN}} \gamma_{\text{Cl}}}{\gamma_{\text{AN}}}$ becomes

zero so that K' is equal to K_1^a , the thermodynamical dissociation constant in pure water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The solutions were prepared from weighed quantities of pure β -resorcylic acid (m. p. 213°) and sodium chloride by adding them to weighed quantities of water. A weighed quantity of standard sodium hydroxide solution (free from carbonate) was run into the solution of the acid and the quantity of sodium salt formed was calculated.

The silver—silver chloride electrode was prepared according to the directions of Carmody (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2901) and the hydrogen electrode according to the method suggested by Branch, Yabroff and Bettman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 937). The hydrogen used for the electrode was prepared by the electrolysis of 10% caustic soda and purified in the manner already described (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1938, **21A**, 373).

The cell (Fig. 1) used in the experiment was made of pyrex glass and was filled with enough solution to dip the hydrogen electrode. For each experiment the electrode was rinsed with solution to be used and the hydrogen was allowed to bubble through the vessel for about 3 hours. The cells were kept in a thermostat maintained at 30° ± 0.02 and the electromotive force readings were taken on a Tinsley's vernier potentiometer.

FIG. 1.

The values of the ionic concentrations of various salts along with the observed electromotive force are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Composition of solutions and E. M. F. of cells.

Solution.	m_{HAc}	m_{NaCl}	m_{NaAc}	μ	E.
I	0.00957	0.03976	0.00864	0.04915	0.5007
II	0.01159	0.03677	0.00773	0.04543	0.4945
III	0.00833	0.02727	0.01137	0.03908	0.5204
IV	0.00755	0.02575	0.00986	0.03648	0.5207
V	0.00961	0.02778	0.00563	0.03415	0.5002
VI	0.00854	0.02184	0.01121	0.03386	0.5242
VII	0.00648	0.01179	0.00466	0.01745	0.5214
VIII	0.00645	0.00563	0.00367	0.01050	0.5344

TABLE II.

Calculation of dissociation constant.

Solution.	m_{H}	$\frac{E - E_{\text{a}}}{0.06012}$	$\log \frac{m_{\text{HAc}} m_{\text{Cl}}}{m_{\text{Ac}}}$	$\log K'$	$K' \times 10^4$
I	0.00075	4.6820	-1.3561	-3.3259	4.722
II	0.00093	4.5792	-1.2586	-3.3206	4.779
III	0.00044	5.0100	-1.6993	-3.3107	4.890
IV	0.00087	5.0150	-1.7051	-3.3099	4.899
V	0.00074	4.6740	-1.3320	-3.3420	4.550
VI	0.00081	5.0732	-1.7789	-3.2943	5.078
VII	0.00100	5.0266	-1.7854	-3.2412	5.738
VIII	0.00123	5.2428	-2.0046	-3.2382	5.779

The plot of μ , the ionic strength against the logarithm of the corresponding dissociation constants shown in Fig. 2 when extrapolated for zero

ionic strength gives 6.05×10^{-4} as the value of K_1^a , the true thermodynamical dissociation constant of β -resorcylic acid in pure water at 30° .

FIG. 2.

The lower values obtained by previous workers (Ostwald and Süss *loc. cit.*) are principally due to the then accepted assumption of incomplete dissociation of the sodium salt and to the lack of corrections for the interionic attractions. The two corrections, however, are of opposite sign.

β -Resorcylic acid has two OH groups in *ortho*- and *para*- positions. We have previously shown that the presence of the hydroxyl group in the *ortho*- position increases (the dissociation constant), while that in the *para*- position decreases. In β -resorcylic acid, therefore, the presence of the hydroxyl group in the *ortho*- position increases the strength of the carboxyl acid, while that in the *para*- position decrease it, so that the order of the strength of the acids is in *ortho*-hydroxybenzoic acid $>$ β -resorcylic acid $>$ benzoic acid. Further work is in progress.

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